

Rac-1ap

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-2-114-S-rac-20%-AD	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	
Vial:	89	Acq. Method Set:	20%qb
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	XT 2 114 S RAC
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	60.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	9/2/2021 10:02:05 PM CST		
Date Processed:	10/26/2021 10:18:47 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	5.367	12944090	49.64	2082981
2	6.396	13131888	50.36	1755839

Asy-1ap

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-2-115-2-s-20%-AD	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	
Vial:	20	Acq. Method Set:	20%qb
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	XT 2 115 S RAC
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	20.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	9/3/2021 7:24:40 PM CST		
Date Processed:	10/26/2021 10:17:04 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	5.347	591677	8.71	96406
2	6.339	6199568	91.29	848444